

Supporting maintenance tasks and upgrading roadworks through an integrated automated system

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TRADITIONAL VS HERON

ROADS ARE CRUCIAL FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND GROWTH, PROVIDING ACCESS TO EDUCATION, HEALTH, AND EMPLOYMENT. THE **MAINTENANCE, REPAIR AND UPGRADE OF ROADS** IS ONE OF THE MOST IMPORTANT PARTS FOR THEIR **HIGH LEVEL SERVICE PROVISION.**

KEY ACTIVITIES OF RI OPERATORS:

- ✓ INSPECTION AND INVENTORYING OF POTHoles AND CRACKS
- ✓ DETECTION AND OF CRACKS
- ✓ INSPECTION AND REPORTING OF ROAD MARKING
- ✓ INSPECTION AND REPLACEMENT OF CUD PAVEMENTS
- ✓ ALL COMBINED WITH PRE-POST INTERVENTION PHASE (CONES PLACEMENT AND REMOVAL)

NEED OF RI OPERATORS

INFRASTRUCTURE OPERATORS AND MAINTENANCE COMPANIES NEEDS:

- ✓ INCREASE OF MAINTENANCE AND UPGRADING TASKS VERSUS TRADITIONAL PROCEDURES;
- ✓ INCREASE OF AREA COVERED BY INSPECTIONS VERSUS TRADITIONAL VISUAL INSPECTION;
- ✓ **DECREASE OF HUMAN INTERVENTION** DURING MAINTENANCE, UPGRADING AND INSPECTION OF RI;
- ✓ DECREASE OF HUMAN INTERVENTION DURING OPERATION, PATROLLING, INVENTORYING AND INSPECTION ACTIVITIES;
- ✓ **COST REDUCTIONS** OF MAINTENANCE AND UPGRADING OF RI VERSUS TRADITIONAL COSTING;
- ✓ COST REDUCTIONS OF OPERATION, PATROLLING, INVENTORYING AND INSPECTION ACTIVITIES;
- ✓ **REDUCTION OF TRAFFIC JAMS.**

TRADITIONAL VS HERON

HERON AIMS TO DEVELOP AN **INTEGRATED AUTOMATED SYSTEM TO PERFORM MAINTENANCE AND UPGRADING ROADWORKS**, I.E. SEALING CRACKS, PATCHING POTHOLES, ASPHALT REJUVENATION, AUTONOMOUS REPLACEMENT OF CUD ELEMENTS AND PAINTING MARKINGS, AND SUPPORTING THE **PRE-/POST- INTERVENTION PHASE** INCLUDING VISUAL INSPECTIONS AND DISPENSING AND REMOVING TRAFFIC CONES IN AN AUTOMATED AND CONTROLLED MANNER.

TRADITIONAL VS HERON

THE HERON SYSTEM WILL CONSIST OF:

- ✓ UGV ACTUATORS
- ✓ UGV / UAV SENSORS
- ✓ ROBOTIC SYSTEM
- ✓ SECURE DATA COMMUNICATION
- ✓ MIDDLEWARE & DF
- ✓ SENSING INTERFACE & AI
- ✓ IMS / DSS / AR

HERON COP – IMS - DSS

- BASED ON PANOPTIS H2020 PROJECT, HERON DSS WILL GRANTS USERS WITH REAL-TIME INFORMATION STREAM ENHANCING THEIR SITUATIONAL AWARENESS THROUGH THE FOLLOWING CAPABILITIES...

HERON COP – IMS - DSS

- ✓ **SOFTWARE-AS-A-SERVICE OR ON PREMISE**
- ✓ **INTEGRATION OF UNIQUE AND DIVERSE TOOLS AND SERVICES FOR RI SITUATIONAL AWARENESS & DECISION SUPPORT**
- ✓ WARNING & ALERTS
- ✓ VIDEO MANAGEMENT
- ✓ UGV/UAV MISSIONS
- ✓ RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND TRACKING
- ✓ EVENT AND INCIDENT MANAGEMENT
- ✓ COLLABORATIVE RESPONSE
- ✓ AR CAPABILITIES FOR DISPLAYING FUNCTIONAL ELEMENTS
- ✓ DASHBOARDS WITH ANALYTICS AND NOTIFICATIONS FOR CONTROL CENTERS

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HERON VALIDATION

Spain

Greece

France

KPIs

KPI_1. MAINTENANCE OPERATORS' COLLABORATION

KPI_2. MANIPULATION TASKS

KPI_3. IMPROVED CV & ML

KPI_4. SLAM ACCURACY AND ROBUSTNESS

KPI_5. VISIBILITY ENHANCEMENT

KPI_6. COGNITION DEVICES INTEGRATED

KPI_7. INTERACTIVE OPERATING CENTRE

HERON IMPLEMENTATION FRAMEWORK

- TITLE: IMPROVED ROBOTIC PLATFORM TO PERFORM MAINTENANCE AND UPGRADING ROADWORKS: THE HERON APPROACH
- ACRONYM: HERON
- GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 955356
- TOTAL COST € 4 998 000
- EU CONTRIBUTION € 4 998 000
- CALL: SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - SMART, GREEN AND INTEGRATED TRANSPORT
- TOPIC: MG-2-10-2020

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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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